

Gholam 'Ali Rásikh

Khan Bahadur Saiyid Zamiruddin Ahmad

Note:

Khan Bahadur Saiyid Zamiruddin Ahmad (1862-January 1922) was one of the members of 'Azimabad's nobility. An aristocrat of noble distinction belonging to the class of educated Muslim elites of Biharsharif, and later 'Azimabad, he graduated from the Presidency College, Calcutta in 1885 with Persian, English, and Philosophy as principal subjects. He chose to reside in Patna after his marriage and lived there till his death. He served as the Honorary Magistrate of Patna. Well versed in Urdu, Persian, and English, he wrote a couple of important books and articles in Urdu and English.

Zamiruddin's Urdu book on the life and teachings of the renowned *Sufi* of Biharsharif, Makhdúm Sharfuddin Ahmad Yahya Maneri, 'Sirat-ul-Sharf' (1901), is regarded as the first notable book on the philosophy of *tasawwuf* as well. The first edition of this book displays his name as Saiyid Zamiruddin Ahmad Bihari 'Azimabadi. Another book in Urdu, 'Kaukaba-e-Mamlúki-o-Malúki' narrates the life and deeds of the rulers of India from Qutbuddin Aibak to Khilji Sultans. Besides rendering 'Tabqat-e-Akbari' into English, he had written historical accounts of Sher Shah, and Daud Khan Quraishi, first Subedar of Bihar (February 1659 - December 1664).

Zamiruddin Ahmad's article on the 'Azimabadi Urdu poet Sheikh Ghulam 'Ali Rásikh appeared in the 'Journal of the Bihar and Orissa Research Society', (Vol. iv, Part 1, March 1918). This is the first-ever introduction to Rásikh's life and poetry written in English. The article contains extensive references to Rásikh's couplets which have been ardently translated into English by the author.

Zamiruddin's son Syed Badruddin Ahmad (1901-1983) was a poet, writer, and politician who authored a memoir of medieval Patna (Azimabad) 'Haqeeqat bhi Kahani bhi: 'Azimabad Ki Tahzeebi Daastaan' (2003). **Arshad Masood Hashmi**

At the downfall of the Moghul Empire in India when the Government of Bengal, Bihar, and Orissa was changing hands there was born in the district of Patna a man named Gholam 'Ali, afterwards known by his pen-name Rásikh, who was destined to leave his mark in the domain of Urdu poetry.

He was born in 1162 A. H. (1749 A. D.). There is no recorded account of his family to trace his descent. It is said that his grandfather came to Bihar from Shahjahanabad (Delhi), and settled here. They say that Rásikh was born at a village called Sáin, which is at a distance of ten or twelve miles from Bankipore, but in his early years, he permanently moved to Patna to take his abode there. Up to his death, however, he never built a house of his own and lived in a tenanted building. It is said that his first teacher in poesy was one Mirza Sharer. Later on, he became a pupil of Mir Taqi Mir of Delhi, who then ruled in India as the enthroned King of Urdu poets. Both Muhammad Husain Azád and 'Ali Muhammad Shád in their books say that Rásikh went to Mir to sit at his feet, but when the latter saw his verses, he told him that he need not bother himself to be his pupil as he himself; to tell the truth, was a past master of poesy. However, on the insistence of the young poet, he simply changed a word or two in one of his verses, and thus impressed upon him his Hall-mark which entitled him to pass as a recognized poet of the Urdu language. In his various verses, Rásikh prides upon his being a pupil of Mir. On the death of the latter, Rásikh was recognized as his true successor. All the other poets of his time recognized him as their *Ustad*. They used to flock at his place and take lessons from him in poesy, Rásikh hints at this in his various verses.

In connection with his writing verses, it is worth mentioning that he never wrote verses unless he first refreshed his mind with the sweet melody of music. He was a very skillful singer and had a singular taste for music. In him music and muse were combined together. He had a very

tender heart. It is said that whenever he read his ghazals in *masha'iras* (parties held for reciting ghazals by several poets) tears dropped down from his eyes and he became so much overpowered by emotion that he could hardly control himself and read out his ghazals to their finish.

He was well-read in Sufism. He was fully familiar with the writings of Mukhdum Shurf-ud-din Ahmad of Bihar, one of the greatest saints of the Muslim world, and during his closing days, as he himself writes to Shah Abul Hassan Furd, *Sajjadahnashin* of Phulwari, he had given himself up to reading books on Sufism. This gives a clue to his being so full of pathos and of love and sympathy for mankind and God's creatures in general.

Lack of recognition of the indigenous talents and abilities, which is a significant characteristic of the Province, compelled him to go abroad and knock at the doors of men of other provinces for help and support. No doubt he got some rewards for his poems, as he himself hints at it, from some of the grandees of his native place, but they were by fits and starts and too insignificant to be of any substantial help to him. He was not a rich man — rather he passed his life in pecuniary difficulties. We find him complaining of this in his various *Musnavies* and also in the letter he wrote to Shah Abul Hassan Furd. He writes to the latter that he was compelled by the vicissitudes of fortune to seek fresh fields and pastures new, and not to stick to his native place — Patna. This letter was written when the writer, as he mentions in the letter, was close upon 70 years of age.

He visited several cities of Upper India, and once in his closing days he went to Calcutta also. He waited upon Ghazi-ud-din Hayder and Asif-ud-Daula of Lucknow and presented a *Musnavi* to each of them. But it is evident that his talents and merits were not fully recognized and rewarded there. Had it been otherwise he would have been fixed to their courts as it was then a customary thing. The reason seems to be this that he did not belong to Upper India, but was a Bihari whom till then and till a long time after the Upper Indians did not consider as their peer in the Urdu language. While in Calcutta he was so hard-pressed for money and was reduced to such serious straits that he could not even pay for his expenses back to his home. He was at last introduced there by Quazi Seraj-ud-dinr Khan Mujid, the *Quaziul-Quzzat* of Calcutta and Maulavi Kashid pen-named Arshud, the *Mufti* of Calcutta to Maharaja Jagurnath Bahadur. The latter appears to have been a patron of men of letters. Rásikh wrote a *Musnavi* and presented it to the Maharaja wherein he fully described his straitened circumstances and appealed to his generosity and sympathy. This must have had its proper effect, because we find Rásikh giving expression to

his sense of gratitude in some of his Ruba-'is for the help rendered by Mujid and Arshud.

As to his religious belief there is a controversy. Both Sunnies and Shi'as claim him to be one of their own sects. There are many verses in his writings in which he praises 'Ali, but at the same time there are verses wherein he praises other Khalifs too. It must be pointed out here that he has not written anything in praise of 'Ali which runs counter to what Sunnies ascribe to 'Ali or which is in excess of what they think of him. As far as I have been able to deduce from his writings, I cannot but say that he was a Sunni and Sufi out and out. The Sufi sect generally adore 'Ali as he is the fountain head of their sect. It is hence that they are so profuse in his praise. With both Sunnies' and Shi'as' love of the descendants of the Prophet is a cardinal principle of their tenets. The difference is simply this, that while one recognizes 'Ali as one of the *Khalifas*, the other recognizes him as the only *Khalifa* and in their zeal speaks ill of the others. Over and above this had Rásikh been a Shi'a, he would not have recognized a Sunni as his Murshid (monitor). We have it in his own handwriting- that he was a disciple of a Phulwari *Sajjadahnashin*. His letter is still preserved in Phulwari. It is written in his own handwriting, and I had the privilege and permission, while I called at the Phulwari Khanquah to read it with my own eyes. A copy thereof was also supplied to me which I still possess.

An article on Rásikh published in the defunct Urdu paper *Alpunch* published in 1903, says that up to 1221 A. H. (1806 A. D.) Rásikh passed his life in shifting from one place to another, but in 1222 he returned to Patna not to leave it again till his death. He died at Patna in his 76 years of age on the 26th Jamadi II, 1238 A. H. (February 1823 A. D.) and was buried at Lodi Kutra, where his tomb, though in a dilapidated condition, still exists.

A complete collection of his writings is to be found in the Bankipore Oriental Library, and a small collection of his works was published about twenty-five years ago by one Mirza Imdad Husain of Patna. The latter no doubt betrays a cruel hand of some plagiarists, still the publisher deserves gratitude of the public for giving an access to Rásikh's writings.

Rásikh as a Poet

Rásikh was a born poet. When a striking event occurred or an unusual feeling moved him, his poetic genius was stirred up and burst forth in verses. His poetic flight soars high to the domains of religion, love, heaven, destiny and the world at large. His light is pure, dry light free from the humours of habit, and purged from consecrated usage. While

no place and no heart is free from love, Rásikh's heart which bore the Hallmark of it and was wounded and tortured by the treacherous treatment of the world, was a mine of pathos and emotion. His verses carry with them cogent proofs of it. He lived at a time when there were still to be found, though more or less faint, traces of the Moghul Empire in the country. Till then foreign manners and customs had not eclipsed the polish and refinement of the Moghal Courts and the etiquettes of Muslim Indian Societies. This had an influence over his language which had assimilated the Court polish by the process of conscious imitation but without mimicry. He had exquisite felicity of choice, his dictionary had no vulgar word in it, no harsh one, but all culled from the luckiest moods of poets, and with a faint but delicious aroma of association, he had a perfect sense of sound, and one idea without which all the poetic outfit is of little avail—that of combination and arrangement. He had no hesitation in his anxiety to gain his end, even to use pure Hindi words, and he did so with such masterly precision that it imparted to his verses a flavour of its own. I shall quote here two couplets of his writings: -

I found its victims confounded;

Those that came over this side were done with.

By its communion men have parted from themselves; They
went to seek union but turned into hermits.

The most striking feature of his verses is that if their metre and rhyme be done away with, they read just like very nicely composed prose. This proves his complete mastery over the language and composition, e.g.,

When hast thou recognized a friend?

Thou art not an acquaintance, rather a stranger.

Thou didst introduce me to a *mushrik* (one who takes a partner
for God),

I did not expect this from thee.

Dost, thou doubt the power of nourishing of the Providence?

Then I doubt your *mominiet* (i.e., your being a Muslim).

He was a happy mixture of originality, elegance, sense, and imagination. He wrote with a beauty of design and finish that are of no time. He tried to satisfy not merely some fleeting fancy of the day, but a constant longing and hunger of human nature. He did not tease his words into a fury in order to infuse them with the deliberate heat of his matured conception, and strived to replace the rapture of the mind with a fervid

intensity of phrase. He was the original man who contrived to be simply natural. His ghazals bear the stamp of maturity as well as youthful freshness. He puts life into the words and retains the attention of the readers. In the main he is more a subjective poet than an objective one. His verses brim over with subjective matters. A large number of them fully indicate that he was brooding over his own internal states and that he owed his success more to his intellectual world than the outside and material one. For similes and metaphors, he has not to travel to regions unknown, but he seizes upon the things around and makes them serve his purpose which gratifies certain known habits of association, e.g., -

If not a beggar at thy door.
Why then when it gets dark?
With her silver bowl
The full moon comes to thy door,
It (i. e., Heaven) has made me a flower of game,
This black-faced is so much bent upon my injury.
How far-reaching is the sight of these eyes!
I found this lance across the heart.
That origin of life is compassing this world in such a way,
As the veil of words is covering the face of meaning.
Why should not the flams of the fire of my heart rise up?
It has been fanned up with the skirt of thy eyelashes.
As within the seeds the forms of plants are hidden.
So, in the knowledge of the Creator was that which has now
been created.

In using allusions, he does not confine himself solely to those events, stories and persons that play parts in Arabic and Persian literatures but he draws upon the Hindu traditions and mythology also. In one of his *musnavies* named 'Husn-o Ishque' (Beauty and Love) where he describes the triumph of 'love', he writes —

The home-comfort was lost by *Damun*
Nul left home on thy account.
Kamrup at last became hermit for thee,

He in the end lost his colour and beauty.
Thou made him shed tears in streams,
Thou made him wander about in the woods.
Thou showed him such a dream,
Which dream created a mischief.

There are many verses in his writings wherein he touches upon the social, moral and economic conditions of his time, e.g., -

Men of low position used to show respects to those of high position in life,

A mean fellow couldn't dare to seek precedence over an honourable man.

The old order has changed. The contrary exists now.

Villains are better off and the virtuous are in ruin and disgrace,

Lowly men are more highly placed than men of respectability.

They occupy a higher position than men of birth.

Those that are in reality a disgrace even to the lowest rank. Often occupy the front place in society.

Those that deserve the front place in Society,

It is with difficulty that they get even a place in the back seats.

Where is olden time? Now the villains are in ascendance.

No *Ra'is* is now to be found who does not favour a mean fellow

What time is it that men call an honest man a fool?

Now ho who tells a lie is considered a wise man.

Do not search for a faithful friend in this age.

There are many friends but a faithful one is more rare [sic] than an 'Anka ['anqa].

In his verses he has touched on various occasions upon philosophical subjects, too, such as 'What was the object of the Creation?', 'Everything of the Universe proves God's existence', 'This world is alluring but at the same time fickle and transitory', etc., etc. I shall give below some of his verses on the points: —

The object of the creation was only His own exhibition.

For looking at Him this mirror was needed.
He had in a way to represent His own glory.
Hence, He became maker of the mirror of the Universe,
No doubt someone is the organizer of the lively congregation of
the world.
Unless there is an organizer, a congregation cannot be so superbly
organized.
There is some active soul hidden,
The method of this scene of activities (i.e., world) indicates this.

Verses embodying admonition and advice are also very copiously met
with in his writings. He misses no opportunity to convey his sound
counsel and advice to his readers, and does so in a very effective manner.
Here are some such verses: —

I found out the latent in the patent,
The painter became visible to me in the painting.
We are morning lamps. What is the value of staying here?
Transitoriness of this fleeting congregation (i.e., world) is too
apparent.
The expanse of the heart of this garden is very tidy. Here under
the cover of each colour a net is placed. The spectator gets from
here nothing but a wound,
I found this orchard totally a bed of *lala* (which looks covered
over with blood).
I have not come to the marketplace of existence by my ownself
Someone has brought me here in order to exhibit himself.
By no means oppress any one
Never think of doing a bad turn.
Do not waste thy life in tyranny,
I mean in this transitory world.
If thou aimest at immortality after death,
And in the future life, paradise,
Leave behind thee a good name.

Carry with thee reward of good deeds.
 Only this one advice suffices thee.
 Keep it in thy mind, and be happy.
 Do not pride upon this life of one breath,
 O ye, fool! the foundation of the fabric of existence rest on the
 surface of air.
 O mean-minded! do not bother thyself so much to hoard money.
 Think of its result from the story of *Quarun's* account.
 In this *Karvansarai* (i.e., this world) there is but fuss and bustle
 of departure,
 It is a place to take a lesson from and not to stay in.
 Yes, plead guilty before God,
 Such is the condition of reverence, albeit thou mayest be not
 guilty.
 So, try that thou mayest gather religious wealth,
 ye, wealthy! how much and what amount is the riches of this
 world?
 Set a value even no y on these cracked glasses.
 Have consideration for the broken heart of the man of faith.
 Do not be enamoured of the beauties of the orchard of the world.
 If thou hast any brain give [sic] thy heart to the embellisher of the
 orchard.
 Stay on in this garden like the aroma of flower.
 So that there may be no difficulty et thy departure.
 Friend! do not tread blindly on the path of seeking (your object).
 Beware! not even a thorn be crushed under thy feet.
 Virtue is independent of appreciation,
 No matter if there is none to appreciate it, but try to be a gem.

In his several works he has touched on many abstruse subjects also.
 Here are extracts from what he has written on Speech (کلام) and love—
 Speech:

The world would be a ruined city.
If the Kingly 'speech' be not there.
If there be no 'speech'
The whole manifestation will be topsy-turvy.
It is the thread of 'speech' which binds tightly.
The ends of the stitching of the two worlds.
The soul of the bodies of the man and the genie is 'speech'.
It is the sweetheart who knows the temper (of the lover).
It is the wine which is congenial to the soul,
Its elation is the support of the soul,
If thou lookest deep.
The silence of the dead man.
Speaks that 'speech' is life,
'Speech' is solace of the lovers.
If there be no 'speech' how before the sweetheart
The lover can pour forth his heart?
The photo of the lover's yearnings,
Is fully visible in this mirror.
'Speech' is a gem from the treasure of life,
The mirror of life owes its reflection to this.
The errand of embassy is settled by this,
The composition is charming and magical on account of this.
It is glow of war and peace.
This magic is fully effective.
Its mode is sometimes love exciting.
Its device is sometimes quarrel-causing.

Love:

Lo! what an extraordinary thing is love.
How dear are its pain and wound!

One is worth concealing in the heart.
One is worth grappling to the breast.
Love keeps aloof from the wise,
Wit has no power to grasp it.
Love is intimate with the wild.
Love is fire for the barn of reputation.
Madness is its agent.
Lunacy is its intimate friend.
It has intimacy with mad men.
It has communion with those that have torn collars,
The position of love is very high,
How can imagination and wit comprehend it?
Ho who has even comprehended a bit of it,
Is crazy, insane and lunatic.
I found its victims confounded.
Those that came over this side were done with.
By its communion men have parted from themselves,
They went to seek union, but turned into hermits.
It is a wonderfully rebellious flame,
It is a spark of fire.
Its heat melts.
Renders stone wax.
It is destructor of intelligence,
It is enchanter and sorcerer,
Though it is cause of the wasting of the body.
Yet it is panacea for the malady of the soul
In lore he who is vanquished triumphs,
Love removes every bar.
Love is seeker as well as sought after.

It is lover as well as beloved.
Its enamoured ones have perplexity.
Love is a power and an elation,
Its inception is to wail,
Its end is to be confounded and perplexed.
It is sum total of the intentions of the book of beauty,
There is in the whole universe a bustle of it only.
Love is pains, afflictions and trouble.
Oh, love is a tremendous affliction!
Love is a fund of hundred distress.
Love is the captivity of the heart.
Love is a malady of the mind.
It has befriended by selections.
Lovers are of diverse conditions.
Some are silent and some prating.
Love is an attraction — Do not question about it (i.e., it is unexplainable).
Love is an allurement — Do not enquire of it (i.e., it is undefinable),
Love is a delight of the Soul.
Love is an ecstatic elation.
In love the contrariety of nature is similarity.
The rank of *Khusró* and *Furhad* is the same,
The method of love is crushing,
This fresh vision is beyond the comprehension of imagination.

It must be borne in mind that the Urdu poetry was born and bred in the laps of the Persian poetry. It was therefore natural that it derived its inspiration from the latter. At the birth of the Urdu poetry the Persian poetry had undergone a complete change in its dictions and thought. The Persian poets had, in order to produce new effects and to give new colours to their verses taken to use subtle, grave, high and remote metaphors and

similes. In their eagerness to court applause, they were ready to sacrifice originality and to give the obscure preference over reality, which meant the stretching out of the shadowy in order to weave a new idea with the warp and woof of unsubstantial things. Hence no foreigners can thoroughly appreciate their verses through mere translation. Many a gap between various words in a verse have to be filled up before it can be intelligible. The Urdu, poets of the time tried to walk in their footsteps and fell in the same trap. Mir, Dard, Sauda, and, almost all the famous poets of the age did not fare better. Rásikh could not have been then an exception. Living at the time of these poets it was natural for him to be impressed with the prevalent ideas of the time. We find hence perceptible marks of this in his ghazal. The following will bear me out: —

After me no unsympathetic hearts will please it.

The pleasure of incarceration of heart will weep for me long.

I passed my youth merrily, now tear shines on eyelashes.

When night closed, there appeared the morning star of old age,

The vanity of wit tries to dislodge me from my position.

Lunacy! do not tarry. Come on; this is the time for help

Rásikh was a copious writer. In every branch of Urdu poetry, he has left us enough to judge of him as a poet. There are many *Quasidas*, *Ruba'is*, *Quat'as* and *Musnavies* besides ghazals which he has left as his legacy to the Urdu-speaking public. But the volumes of his ghazals and *Musnavies* eclipse the others and of these two the latter is more voluminous than the former. In the printed edition of his work there are to be found 14 *Musnavies*. They are as follows: —

(i) Beauty and Love (ii) Coquetry and Supplication (iii) Means of Salvation (iv) Attraction of Love (v) Magic of Love (vi) Absorption of Love (vii) Miracle of Love (viii) Light of Eye sight (ix) Treasury of Beauty (x) Mirror of Beauty (xi) Love Letters (xii) Details of Circumstances (xiii) Ruin of a City (xiv) Eulogium.

Some of them had been written to orders and some by the necessity of the occasion, but none of them seem to be laboured. In them he had not to play the part of a didactic poet, but that of a tentative one and so he gathers as he goes and enlarges the scope of his vision at each step he makes. He does not go back upon and recast his diction so as to give his composition those lineaments of truth and nature on which its effect as a whole depends. For in such a work, that which, above all things, the reader ought to see is the progression of effect, which the study of subject,

exhibited in the actual tissue of the poem, has had upon the mind of the poet. In language and finish they are superb, and fully establish his mastery over the metrical language.

The 'Beauty and Love' was written to be presented to Vazirul-Momalik Raf'at-ud-Daula Rafial-Mulk Ohazi-ud-din Hayder Khan Bahadur Shahamat Jung of Lucknow. The 'Attraction of Love' was written to be presented to Vazirul-Momalik Asif-ud-Daula Bahadur of Lucknow. The 'Details of Circumstances' was presented to Maha- rajah Jagurnath Bahadur at Calcutta wherein the poet details his own straitened circumstances and appeals to the sympathy and generosity of the Maharajah.

The 'Treasury of Beauty' was written at the instance of the poet's patron Mir Mehdi 'AH Khan, who was *Naib* of Mir Quasim Khan in Patna and who figured so prominently in the battle of Patna against the English. In this poem Rásikh gives a eulogistic description of a songstress and dancing-girl named Shurfu who appears, from the tone of the poem, to have been under the protection of Mehdi 'Ali Khan and with whom the poet himself was in love. He says: —

My heart is enchanted only of that idol.
Whose name, God save her, is Shurfu,
Love of none but that flower exists in my heart.
This very fire is burning within my body.

In the 'Mirror of Beauty' he gives in a very charmingly interesting manner description of a party given at the house of one Amin-ud-din Ahmad in Calcutta, whereat the poet was present. The reader gets a glimpse into the state of Society that prevailed in Calcutta in those days. The dancing-girl and songstress who danced and sang there has been drawn with a deft hand and her attraction has been depicted in a skilful manner, and invested with a considerable charm.

In 'The Ruin of a City' he laments over the ruin and decay — economic, social and moral — which had overtaken Patna in the poet's time. He gives a very pathetic account of all classes of people and professions. The 'Light of the Eyesight' was written in imitation of J'ami's *سبحه الاسرار* (Subhat-ul-Asrar) and Khusrú's *مطلع الانوار* (Matl-a ul Anwar). This is rather the first and the last of its kind written in the Urdu language, and it is no exaggeration to say that Rásikh has acquitted himself in it very creditably. He has divided the poem into various

Munzers (landscapes)— each with a small opening for looking through at the stories he gives under each Munzer.

The ‘Coquetry and Supplication’ is the best of Rásikh’s *Musnavies* — rather the best in the Urdu Language. In language, in diction, in style, in rhyme, and in pathos and emotion it is peerless in the whole range of the Urdú literature.

In several of his *Musnavies* he incidentally describes some of the Indian cities, such as Benares, Faizabad, Lucknow, Patna and Calcutta, and the descriptions given are worth reading.

He wrote many *Quasidas* mostly in praise of the *Umarás* of his time which are of very high water-mark and which place their author in the front rank of the Urdu poets. From them one can easily know which of the *Umarás* of those days commanded political and social influence in the province or in the neighbouring *Subás* and ruled over the hearts of the afflicted and the poor. There is a *Quasida* in praise of Nawab Shums-ud-Daula Mr. Henry Vansittart, Governor of Bengal, too. In this *Quasida* even after making allowance for poetic exaggeration, there is much to indicate that the English Nawab was held in high estimation by the people. Besides *Quasidas* there are to be found in the Collection of Rásikh’s works *Vasokhts*, *Mursiahs*, *Mosudduses*, *Turjibunds*, *Quit’as*, *Ruba’is*, etc., etc., but these, though prove versatility of the poet’s pen, are too numerous to be dealt with separately and with any length.